

REACTIONS OF CHLORIDES OF SULPHUR WITH ASPIRIN AND ACETOXY- β -NAPHTHOL

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Aspirin with sulphur di- or monochloride yielded sulphides in which hydrolysis had taken place. Acetoxy- β -naphthol with sulphur mono- and dichloride afforded plastic mass, but with sulphur trichloride it yielded a sulphide without undergoing hydrolysis. Acetoxy- β -naphthol reacted with thionyl chloride yielding a mixture of 2:2'-diacetoxy- and 2:2'-dichloro-dinaphthyl sulphides.

Acetyl derivatives of sulphides of β -naphthol and salicylic acid were needed as starting materials in connection with some other work on hand and had to be prepared by first obtaining the sulphides according to the method followed by Airan and Shah (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1940, 9, Part III, 120) and then by acetylating the sulphides so obtained. It therefore occurred to us to treat straightway acetoxy- β -naphthol and aspirin with chlorides of sulphur.

It was found that aspirin with either sulphur dichloride or monochloride yielded sulphides in which hydrolysis had taken place. With sulphur dichloride it forms, in addition to the already known (Hirwe, Jadhav and Chakradeo, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 101) monosulphide, a trisulphide, whereas with sulphur monochloride a tetrasulphide is obtained. Even when, instead of chloroform, glacial acetic acid was used as the medium, the acetoxy group was hydrolysed and a similar course of reaction took place.

Acetoxy- β -naphthol, on the other hand, gave with both these chlorides only a plastic mass. On treatment with thionyl chloride, however, it yielded a mixture of 2:2'-diacetyldinaphthyl sulphide (Airan and Shah, *loc. cit.*) and 2:2'-dichlorodinaphthyl sulphide. Thus, a portion of acetoxy- β -naphthol seems to have reacted to form the sulphide without undergoing hydrolysis. At the same time, another portion, apparently during the sulphide formation, underwent hydrolysis, the OH group so formed ultimately being replaced by Cl. For, the resulting sulphide does not seem to have yielded to the treatment calculated to bring about either acetylation or hydrolysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reaction of Sulphur Dichloride with Aspirin.—Aspirin (20 g.) was suspended in chloroform (100 c.c.) and sulphur dichloride (7 c.c.) was added in the presence of zinc chloride (0.2 g.) used as a catalyst. Slowly at the room temperature a clear red solution was formed and then a solid began to separate out. When allowed to stand overnight, it yielded a total of 12 g. of the product, m.p. 255-60°. On crystallisation from glacial acetic acid, two fractions were obtained:

The first fraction (I) melted at 273-74°, and the second (II) at 220-21°. Both contained sulphur and gave ferric chloride test for hydroxyl group.

[Found (compound I): S, 10.58. $C_{14}H_{10}O_6S$ requires S, 10.46 per cent].

[Found (compound II): S, 25.72. $C_{14}H_{10}O_6S_2$ requires S, 25.95 per cent].

The former was found to be identical with 3:3'-dicarboxy-4:4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide, reported by Hirwe, Jadhav and Chakradeo (*loc. cit.*).

Nitration of Compound (II).—Compound (II, 2 g.) was refluxed with 50 c.c. of 10% nitric acid for 2 hours. The mixture was rapidly filtered while hot. On cooling,

a white solid separated, which on crystallisation from water melted at 226-27°. It contained nitrogen but no sulphur. It was found to be identical with 5-nitrosalicylic acid (m.p. 227°), reported by Hirwe *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

Reaction of Sulphur Monochloride with Aspirin.—Aspirin (20 g.) was treated in chloroform with sulphur monochloride (7 c.c.) as described earlier. Here also a total of 13 g. of the product was obtained. On crystallising it from glacial acetic acid only one compound melting at 231-32° was obtained. It contained sulphur and also gave ferric chloride test for the hydroxyl group. Its mixed melting point with compounds (I) and (II) showed depression. (Found: S, 31.86. $C_{14}H_{10}O_6S_2$, requires S, 31.84 per cent).

Nitration of compound (III); was effected in the same manner as described above and a product (m.p. 226-27°), identical with the one mentioned above, was obtained.

Changing the Medium from Chloroform to Glacial Acetic Acid

(a). *With Sulphur Dichloride as the Reagent.*—Same proportions and conditions, as when chloroform was used as medium, were maintained. Instead of the reaction product separating out the same day, in this case, a period of two days was required. Both the trisulphide (m.p. 220-21°) and the monosulphide (273-74°) were obtained as before.

(b). *With Sulphur Monochloride as the Reagent.*—Here also similar conditions were maintained and only the tetrasulphide (m.p. 231-32°) was obtained.

Reaction of Sulphur Dichloride and Monochloride with Acetoxy- β -naphthol.—Acetoxy- β -naphthol, dissolved in 25 c.c. of chloroform, was treated once with sulphur dichloride (3 c.c.) and then with sulphur monochloride (3 c.c.) in the presence of zinc chloride (0.2 g.). Since no solid separated on keeping the mixture overnight, the solvent was removed by distillation, when in both the cases only a plastic mass was obtained from which no crystalline solid could be recovered.

Reaction of Acetoxy- β -naphthol with Thionyl Chloride.—Acetoxy- β -naphthol (5 g.) was treated with thionyl chloride (12 c.c.) in the presence of zinc chloride (0.2 g.). The compound dissolved slowly forming a clear greenish yellow solution. It was then kept overnight, when a solid separated. Excess of thionyl chloride was removed by distillation and the residue was washed with ether. The crude yellow solid (3 g.) was then treated with hot acetic acid when most of the solid dissolved, leaving behind a small yellow residue. The filtrate, on cooling, gave a crystalline white solid, m.p. 197-98° and it was identical with 2:2'-diacetyxydinaphthyl sulphide reported by Airan and Shah (*loc. cit.*).

The yellow residue was then purified by washing it with hot alcohol in a soxhlet as this was found to be insoluble in most of the common solvents. It melted at 270-71° and contained both sulphur and chlorine. Its mixed melting point with 2:2'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide and 2:2'-diacetyxydinaphthyl sulphide, reported by Airan *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), showed depression. (Found: S, 9.315; Cl, 20.4. $C_{20}H_{12}Cl_2S$ requires S, 9.014; Cl, 20.0 per cent).

This compound remained unaffected when refluxed with acetic anhydride or alcoholic potash.